

INVESTIGATION OF THE DYNAMIC BEHAVIOUR OF EPOXY REINFORCED NANOSILICA AND MICROPARTICULATE RUBBER COMPOSITES THROUGH ANALYTICAL-EXPERIMENTAL TRANSFER FUNCTIONS

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ABSTRACT

An efficient identification method for modal testing of viscoelastic composite materials such as epoxy reinforced with nanosilica and carboxyl-terminated butadiene acrylonitrile copolymer (CTBN) rubber is demonstrated in this paper, through the analytical-experimental transfer function method. The modal properties, such as resonant frequencies and modal loss factors, are measured by vibrating cantilever beam specimens with an impact hammer, while the vibratory response is detected through an acceleration transducer. The procedure for the identification of analytical-experimental transfer functions is carried out using a genetic algorithm (GA) by minimizing the difference between the measured response from tests and the calculated response, which is a function of the modal parameters. The analytical transfer functions provide a sub-structuring process to identify modes, as a function of damped natural frequencies and loss factors of a complex structure and it is insensitive to experimental noise as well as the modal coupling effect. The validation of the proposed method is verified with a 10-degree-freedom mass-spring-dashpot model. The effectiveness of the proposed method is demonstrated by investigating the static and dynamic behaviour of epoxy cantilever beam specimens reinforced with silica nanoparticles and CTBN rubber inclusions. Analytical-experimental transfer functions were identified for concentrations of 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25wt% for both CTBN and nanosilica, as well as for neat epoxy resin which served as reference sample. The results indicate that either silica nanoparticles or CTBN particles can improve the damping capacity of the epoxy-based composites. However, it was observed that in the case of reinforcing the epoxy with CTBN particles, the stiffness of the composites was dramatically reduced.

1 INTRODUCTION

In response to a transient or dynamic loading, there is a wide set of structural components or assemblies for which vibration is directly related to performance, either by virtue of causing temporary malfunction during excessive motion or by creating disturbance or discomfort, such as stress fatigue failure, premature wear, operator discomfort, unsafe operating condition and high noise levels. For all these potential problems, it is important that the in-service or operation vibration levels that usually encountered in structures have to be predicted and brought under satisfactory control [1, 2]. Thus, it is vital to determine the elastic material properties and the modal parameters, i.e. damped natural frequencies of the structure to avoid resonance, damping factors and mode shapes to reinforce the most flexible points or to determine the exact points so to reduce weight or to increase damping. In

general, the dynamic response of a system depends on geometric and material properties. Elastic properties of composites can be determined by semi-static or dynamic mechanical tests. Static mechanical tests are destructive, while the majority of dynamic mechanical tests offer the advantage of being non-destructive. With respect to these dynamic aspects, nano-reinforced polymeric composites represent an excellent possibility to design components considering the requirements of the dynamic behaviour.

In the past, the damping capacity of conventional engineering materials has not generally provided sufficient energy dissipation to limit resonant or near-resonant amplitudes of vibration. It would therefore be of interest to investigate new materials that simultaneously exhibit high damping capacity with high stiffness and low density including polymer matrix nanocomposites. High damping capacity is an important factor for various industrial applications; therefore, it is necessary to develop structural components with a high level of mechanical damping. High loss factor polymers have been used in the past for modern damping applications [3-5]. Nowadays there is a plethora of various other advanced materials that could be utilised in damping applications. Researchers have concentrated their efforts towards the development of polymers in which nanomaterials are embedded in polymer substrates and much promising results have been established primarily for improvement of the mechanical properties [6-9]. Moreover, for damping improvement, epoxy resins reinforced with CTBN rubber are promising materials due to their large recoverable strain and high damping response. Adding rubber particulates (reactive liquid rubber CTBN) into polymer resin is an approach to effectively improve the damping behaviour of composites [10]. In general, embedding such inclusions into a polymeric matrix system, can effectively improve the ductility as well as the fracture toughness of the polymeric composites [11]. The fracture toughness is an important property in fibre polymer composite industry, since it prevents delamination damage, while it is also vital in composite repair procedures [12, 13]. CTBN toughening could be used to arrest any propagated cracks in the repair bondline. Nevertheless, the drawback in doing so is the substantial reduction of the Young's modulus [14]. Chen et al. [15] introduced the hydroxyl functionality of the silica nanoparticles (12 nm) into DGEBA resin to form silica/epoxy nanocomposites, indicating that both Young's modulus and the loss factor of nanocomposites were improved by the silica nanoparticles. The enhancing phenomenon could be due to the low cross-linking density as well as the plasticizing effect caused by the chemical reaction of epoxy with the functional groups grafted on silica surface.

The proposed modal analysis algorithm derives modal parameters from the transfer functions (TFs) of the composites by a curve-fitting technique. Curve-fitting is applied to these TFs in order to determine preliminary modal parameters, from which analytical expressions for the TFs are obtained. These analytical expressions are then employed as the TF input to the standard Asher method [16]. The important characteristic of Asher's method is its capability of identifying individual modes in regions of high modal density. There are several advantages in obtaining analytically-synthesized transfer functions by curve-fitting experimental data [17-19]. Significant data reduction is achieved and initial estimates of natural frequencies are provided. Moreover, such a method permits interpolation between experimental data points to establish resonance frequencies more accurately, while noisy experimental data can be smoothed out.

In the present paper, an optimization algorithm for modal analysis and identification of experimentally defined transfer functions is demonstrated. Mechanical and vibration tests have been conducted in order to determine the dynamic mechanical properties of DGEBA/F epoxy resin reinforced with silica nanoparticles and CTBN rubber inclusions. The results of the viscoelastic and dynamic response of the various concentrations of nanosilica and CTBN rubber were compared with the neat epoxy resin.

2 MATERIALS AND TEST METHODS

2.1 Preparation of epoxy/CTBN rubber and epoxy/nanosilica composites

The epoxy resin that has been used to form the rubber and nanosilica reinforced composites was a standard diglycidyl ether of bis-phenol A/F (DGEBA/F) with an epoxide equivalent weight (EEW) of 169,7 g/eq., supplied by Gurit, UK. The reactive liquid rubber, which gives rise to the micrometer-sized spherical rubber particles upon curing of the formulation, was a carboxyl-terminated butadiene-

acrylonitrile (CTBN) rubber. It was supplied as 40wt% CTBN-epoxy adduct, 'Albipox 1000' (EEW = 330 g/eq), from Evonik, Germany. The curing agent was a 3-aminomethyl-3,5,5-trimethylcyclohexylamine (SP115 Hardener with amine-hydrogen equivalent weight of 42,3 g/eq.), also supplied by Gurit, UK. In order to prepare a series of composites with 10–25 wt% rubber content, the SP115 epoxy resin was mechanically mixed with Albipox 1000-DGEBA/F masterbatch for 30min. The mixture was degassed for 15 min in a vacuum oven to remove the entrapped air, which then was blended with the appropriate stoichiometric amounts of SP115 Hardener (based on the amount of DGEBA and the masterbatch) for 10 min. The rubber modified resin was afterwards degassed in the vacuum oven before curing to remove any air entrapped in the mixture and then poured into a silicon mould. Finally, the resin system was room temperature cured at 24hours following 16 hours at 50°C with a ramp rate of 1°C/min followed by cooling down to room temperature at 1°C/min.

The silica (SiO₂) nanoparticles with a defined size of 20 nm were supplied as a colloidal silica-sol at a concentration of 40 wt% in a DGEBA epoxy resin (EEW= 295 g/eq.) as 'Nanopox F400' from Evonik. The silica nanoparticles are synthesised from an aqueous sodium silicate solution. Then they undergo a process of surface modification, with an organosilane, and matrix exchange to produce a masterbatch of 40 wt% silica nanoparticles in the epoxy resin. The curing procedure was followed as previously described.

Tensile specimens having a 4 mm thickness were manufactured in a silicone rubber mould. The length of the specimens was 150 mm. The length and width of narrow section were 10 and 4 mm, respectively. At least five measurements were machined for testing. Additionally, rectangular specimens with 160mm long, 20mm wide, and 4mm in thickness were also manufactured for the vibration tests. For each particulate epoxy/nanosilica and epoxy/CTBN composite at least three specimens were prepared.

2.2 Mechanical tests

Tensile tests were performed at room temperature (23°C) on a Zwick Z010 (Zwick, Germany) universal testing machine at a constant crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. The measurements followed the EN ISO 527 testing standard using dumbbell shaped specimens. E-moduli were calculated within the linear part of the stress-strain curves. The local microstructure of the fractured areas of the specimens was qualitatively examined using a JEOL JSM-840A scanning electron microscope (SEM).

2.3 Vibration tests and signal processing

The experimental apparatus for the forced vibration tests is shown in Fig.1, where the specimen is clamped on rigid support as a cantilever beam and vibrated by the impact hammer with a high-quality piezoelectric force transducer (Endevco Model 2302-10). The force-hammer was used to apply an initial vibration (input signal) on the free boundary where the specimen was subjected to free damped vibration. In addition, the vibratory response at the specimen tip (output signal) was detected through an acceleration transducer with a sensitivity of 100 mV/g (Brüel & Kjaer 4507B), mounted on the free boundary, while the sensing cables were kept in a free state, thereby having a little influence on the vibration test. For impact excitation, an acquisition and realtime-analysis routine provided digital filtering for two-channel acquisition. So both the force and acceleration analog signals are acquired by an analog-to-digital converter (FFT analyzer PULSE Brüel & Kjaer), while the corresponding results were recorded in a computer. The sampling frequency of acceleration signals was 8192 Hz. Each specimen was measured 10 times and the average value was obtained. In order to acquire the specimen's modal properties from the transient vibration, the Fourier Transforms of both the excitation and the response signals were calculated. The ratio of response to excitation functions was computed to obtain an expression from the corresponding transfer function. The response was calculated in terms of displacement, velocity or acceleration and as a result different terms have been used for the ratios of response to force. This study is focused on displacement responses and any reference to the TF expresses the receptance (dynamic compliance) of the system. The displacement is determined through a double integration process of the experimental data of the accelerometer sensor. High pass filters have been used to remove the DC components and avoid the integrated errors. Thus, the ratio of the resulted displacement to the applied force was computed in order to obtain the

receptance transfer function.

Figure 1: Experimental setup of vibration tests.

3 PROPOSED METHOD AND VERIFICATION OF IDENTIFICATION RESULTS

3.1 Experimental transfer functions

A transfer function G for a single degree of freedom system can be plotted in the Argand (complex) plane by its real and imaginary components as shown in Fig.2. The Argand or Nyquist plane plot is a very effective way of displaying the important resonance region. The amplitude is plotted as the vector X_i at angle θ_i from the real axis, where θ_i is the phase angle between exciting force and the displacement response at frequency ω_i . Through a circle-fitting method a modal circle can be established, which provides the means of extracting the required modal parameters of the system. This method exploits the fact that in the vicinity of a resonance the behaviour of most systems is dominated by a single mode. The response of each mode as it passes through resonance will lie on an arc of a circle [20].

The first step of the algorithm is the automatic selection of a fixed number of points on either side of any identified maximum arc length on the curve for equal frequency increments. Thus, the points ω_{d-1} and ω_{d+1} correspond to the largest arc length l_{imax} , while the resonance frequency ω_d would be midway between ω_{d-1} and ω_{d+1} .

At the second step the procedure followed was to fit a circle through the selected points of the resonance region of the curve and establish the center and the radius of the circle, considered as a least square minimization problem. By calculating the radii through the points on the arc, l_{imax} , the largest angle a included between two adjacent radii can be defined. The loss factor (n) can be computed from:

$$n = \frac{2\Delta\omega}{\omega_d \tan(a/2)} = \frac{2(\omega_{d+1} - \omega_{d-1})}{\omega_d \tan(a/2)} \quad (\text{for } a/2 < 45^\circ) \quad (1)$$

An equivalent Young's modulus is identified from measured complex transfer functions. The constant quantity $G(\omega_i)$ at $\omega_i = 0$ defines the static response factor $G(0)$ (distance OP in Fig.2). This real particular parameter to be adjusted as the proportional gain of the system is identical with the compliance $1/K$, the inverse value of the spring K of the vibratory system for a single degree of freedom. For fixed-free boundary conditions, the stiffness of the system is $K = 3EI/L^3$, where $I = bh^3/12$ is the moment of inertia for a rectangular beam and L is the free length of the cantilever beam. Thus, the elastic modulus can be determined from the first mode of the transfer function by the following equation:

$$E = KL^3/3I \quad (2)$$

The viscoelastic response of materials under test can be expressed by the following equation:

$$n = \frac{E''}{E'} \quad (3)$$

where the quantity E' is called storage modulus, because it defines the energy stored in the specimen due to the applied strain and it is conceptually identical to E elastic modulus. The quantity E'' defines the dissipation of energy and is called the loss modulus.

Figure 2: Complex transfer function of a single degree of freedom system.

3.2 Verification of the proposed method

An accurate mathematical model is a prerequisite of identification procedure by the proposed method. The validation of the proposed method is verified with the calculation of the modal properties of a 10-degree-freedom mass-spring-dashpot model. The model's dynamic properties (inertia M , stiffness K , and damping C) are shown in Table 1.

Dynamic Property	Mode number									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
M [kg]	156	139	122	105	88	77	54	37	20	3
K [N/m] $\times 10^6$	253	223.3	193.3	163.3	133.3	103.3	73.3	43.3	13.3	13.3
C [Ns/m] $\times 10^3$	11.3	10.04	8.75	7.46	5.42	4.08	3.55	2.28	0.93	0.36

Table 1: Dynamic properties of the 10-degree-freedom mass-spring-dashpot model

For analytical mode characterization, a genetic algorithm (GA) optimization technique has been used to fit experimental transfer function data with a set of superimposed, single-mode response functions. It can be shown [21] that the analytical receptance function of n -DOF system for input $f_i(t)$ and output $x_j(t)$ can be written as:

$$G_{ij}(j\omega) = \frac{X_j}{F_i}(j\omega) = \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{U_{ijk} + jV_{ijk}}{\delta_k + j(\omega - \omega_{dk})} + \frac{U_{ijk} - jV_{ijk}}{\delta_k + j(\omega + \omega_{dk})} \right) \quad (4)$$

where U_{ijk} , V_{ijk} are the amplitudes of the residue of the k -th mode, δ_k is the attenuation exponent of the k -th mode, ω is the angular frequency, ω_{dk} is the damped natural frequency of the k -th mode, and n is the order of the curve fit. For an underdamped (light damping) mode k , the attenuation exponent and the damped natural frequency can be related with the loss factor n_k by $\delta_k = (n_k/2)\omega_{nk}$ and $\omega_{dk} = \omega_{nk}\sqrt{1 - (n_k/2)^2}$. The task undertaken is basically to find the variables U, V in this theoretical expression of the transfer function, which matches closely the measured data. It is common in many minimization problems that the least-square error between two responses is selected as a measure of the response difference. Therefore, the summation of the square of the difference between the calculated and measured receptances over a concerned frequency range can be defined as an identification index. The objective function selected in this study can be described by:

$$\text{Objective function } f = \sum_{k=1}^n \left(1 - \frac{G_{ij}(j\omega)_{\text{experimental}}}{G_{ij}(j\omega)_{\text{analytical}}} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

where $G_{ij}(j\omega)$ are the experimental and analytical complex transfer functions. GA has the advantage of seeking the whole space of solutions as well as not being entrapped in a local minimum. The flowchart of the whole identification process of the proposed algorithm is illustrated in Fig.3. Using Eq.4 the fitness function is defined as shown in Eq.5 and is used in all steps of the algorithm. In the first loop of the GA, starting populations are randomly generated to set variables values, which are used to calculate the fitness function value. GA uses selection, elitism, crossover and mutation procedures to create new generations. The new generations converge towards a minimum that is not necessarily the global one. After repetitions when the maximum generations' number is achieved the variables' values corresponding to the minimum fitness function value (ϵ) are selected as the optimum variables values of the GA. The usage of random numbers in GAs [22] to produce the individuals of each generation gives the ability to explore the whole space of solutions.

Figure 3: Flowchart for the identification process of the genetic algorithm.

For this 10-DOF system, modal analysis was implemented in order to determine the eigenfrequencies, the eigenmodes while the TFs of the system were computed. Subsequently, these TFs were imported into the proposed algorithm as input measured data, so new modal parameters and TFs were identified. The results of the identification procedure are illustrated in Fig.4. The GA returned an optimal analytical transfer function which accurately fitted the numerical data of the mode superposition technique. The table in Fig.4 shows the transfer function parameters, as damped natural frequencies and the loss factors. From the values in the table, a conclusion can be drawn by comparing the current identification results with those calculated numerically. It is clear that they are very close to each other.

Figure 4: Identified transfer functions compared with those of 10-DOF mass-spring-dashpot model.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Mechanical behaviour of the epoxy/nanosilica and epoxy/CTBN composites

The calculation of the moduli from the stress-strain graphs reveal that nanosilica particles tend to increase the elastic modulus of the neat epoxy resin in contrary to the rubber particles. The values of the moduli are shown in Table 2. The topography of the fracture surfaces of the epoxy-based nanocomposites and rubber toughened composites is of particular interest. The fracture surfaces of specimens having neat epoxy resin samples showed characteristic river lines and a smooth surface as shown in Fig.5(a). This type of fracture behaviour is typical of brittle epoxy surfaces indicating low resistance to spontaneous crack propagation which was monitored during tensile testing of specimens. All rubber toughened composites and silica nanocomposites revealed a fracture surface with severely distracted patterns. In particular, the specimens with high CTBN concentrations revealed the characteristic inclusions from the rubber particles and plastic behaviour of the epoxy in Fig.5(b). The synergic effects of localized cavitations at the rubber/matrix interface and plastic shear yielding in the epoxy matrix are supposed to be responsible for deformation that results in energy dissipation process which ultimately improves the toughness values of the rubber-modified epoxies and reduces the modulus. It should be noted that the SEM used in the current work is incapable of revealing the details in a nano level, as illustrated in Fig.5(c). It is believed though that for the silica nanoparticle specimens the particle-matrix interfacial adhesion is indeed strong. This is probably because the silica nanoparticles were beforehand surface-modified with silane coupling agent, which can react with both inorganic particles and epoxy resin and yield strong interfacial adhesion which results in the increase in moduli as monitored from the tensile tests.

Engineering Constant	Neat epoxy	Nanosilica (wt%)					CTBN (wt%)				
		5	10	15	20	25	5	10	15	20	25
E [MPa]	3815	4087	4211	4582	5602	5819	3550	3245	2630	2037	1686

Table 2: Elastic moduli of the epoxy/nanosilica and epoxy/CTBN composites from tensile tests.

Figure 5: SEM micrographs of: (a) neat epoxy, (b) 25wt% rubber modified epoxy showing the rubber particle inclusions, (c) 25wt% silica nanocomposites.

4.2 Identified transfer functions

The analytical functions identified the resonance in all three important flexural modes. These mathematically synthesized transfer functions contain all the important resonance information while interpolation among measured data is considered satisfactory. Fig.6 shows the comparison between the identified and measured complex TFs of the specimens.

The identified resonant frequencies of the specimens with different inclusions are shown in Table 3. It is obvious that the frequencies of the first mode increase with respect to the nanosilica content, while the frequencies tend to decrease with the CTBN rubber addition. This was expected since the nanosilica particles increase the stiffness of the epoxy system. The increase in frequency is not considerable because embedding such inclusions into the epoxy matrix leads to heavier specimen. On the other hand, the rubber addition decreases the stiffness of the epoxy network due to the lower stiffness of the rubber itself and probably the reduction in cross-linking density.

Figure 6: Identified complex transfer functions for (a) Neat epoxy, (b) CTBN 25wt% and (c) Nanosilica 25wt% specimens.

Specimen	First frequency [Hz]	Second frequency [Hz]	Third frequency [Hz]
Neat epoxy resin	83.50	445.00	1232.50
Nanosilica 5wt%	85.50	492.50	1251.50
Nanosilica 10wt%	86.50	493.50	1276.50
Nanosilica 15wt%	88.50	500.50	1271.50
Nanosilica 20wt%	91.50	502.50	1288.50
Nanosilica 25wt%	92.50	504.50	1303.50
CTBN 5wt%	75.50	434.50	1177.50
CTBN 10wt%	72.50	402.50	924.50
CTBN 15wt%	69.50	382.50	853.50
CTBN 20wt%	55.50	332.50	799.50
CTBN 25wt%	49.50	258.50	766.50

Table 3: Resonant frequencies of the important flexural modes of the specimens.

4.3 Determination of elastic modulus, loss modulus and loss factor with TF method

The first mode of vibration was used in order to calculate the (E') and (E'') moduli. The compliance of each beam specimen was calculated from identified transfer functions and the elastic modulus was determined. The results of the elastic moduli for the epoxy/nanosilica and the epoxy/CTBN rubber specimens (Table 4) show a good agreement between the value found by tensile tests and the proposed TF method, considering the absolute differences.

The loss modulus is proportional to the (E') and (n) values, and it is related to the energy dissipation mechanisms in materials. The loss modulus is a combination of energy dissipation mechanisms from the matrix material, the inclusions and the interface between them. So, in this case, the energy dissipation due to interfacial adhesion can be of major importance.

Specimen	E from TF method [MPa]	Absolute difference compared to tensile tests (%)
Neat epoxy resin	4017	5%
Nanosilica 5wt%	4313	8%
Nanosilica 10wt%	4524	7%
Nanosilica 15wt%	4857	6%
Nanosilica 20wt%	5327	5%
Nanosilica 25wt%	5590	4%
CTBN 5wt%	3302	7%
CTBN 10wt%	3061	6%
CTBN 15wt%	2828	8%
CTBN 20wt%	1814	11%
CTBN 25wt%	1451	14%

Table 4: Elastic moduli of the specimens determined with TF method compared to tensile tests.

Specimen	E'' [MPa]	Loss factor n	Improvement (%)
Neat epoxy resin	147.82	0.0368	-
Nanosilica 5wt%	205.32	0.0476	29%
Nanosilica 10wt%	222.60	0.0492	34%
Nanosilica 15wt%	242.83	0.0500	36%
Nanosilica 20wt%	277.00	0.0520	41%
Nanosilica 25wt%	307.45	0.0550	49%
CTBN 5wt%	155.84	0.0472	28%
CTBN 10wt%	163.46	0.0534	45%
CTBN 15wt%	173.67	0.0614	67%
CTBN 20wt%	123.69	0.0682	85%
CTBN 25wt%	121.57	0.0838	128%

Table 5: Loss moduli and loss factors of the specimens.

Table 5 shows the values of the loss factor (n) and the loss modulus (E'') for the tested specimens. The addition of both the nanosilica and CTBN particles in the epoxy matrix has improved the damping behaviour. This improvement induced by the CTBN rubber particles could be attributed to their good dispersion within the epoxy as well as the reduced cross-linking density of epoxy itself. It has been also shown in another study [10] that the damping properties of an epoxy resin can be modified by adding nanosilica and CTBN rubber particles. The results in the current work verifies the fact that when the epoxy is loaded with 25wt% CTBN particles the highest loss factor value among the other

concentrations can be attained, with an improvement of 128% compared with the neat epoxy resin (Table 5).

5 CONCLUSIONS

The overall objective of the proposed modal testing method is to determine a set of dynamic mechanical properties of viscoelastic composite materials. This procedure consists of three steps; measure an appropriate set of transfer functions, analyse these using appropriate curve-fitting procedures, combine these results of the curve-fits to construct the required mathematical model of the structure. The last step is usually taken in order to reduce vast quantity of actual measurements to a small and efficient data set. This reduction process has an additional benefit of eliminating small inconsistencies which will inevitably occur in measured data. Given that the modal parameters were defined, the elastic modulus of the composite material can be deduced. Compared with a static testing method, the proposed method is low-cost, convenient and accurate. Furthermore, the proposed modal testing method is non-destructive. A numerical example shows that the proposed algorithm is efficient and robust in identifying the modal parameters of 10-DOF linear system. The proposed modal testing technique has been implemented to investigate the dynamic mechanical properties of nanosilica and CTBN reinforced epoxy composites. Either silica nanoparticles or CTBN particles have shown improvement of the damping capacity of the epoxy-based composites. However, it was observed that in the case of reinforcing the epoxy with CTBN particles, the stiffness of the composites was dramatically reduced. Potentially, the low modulus can be compensated with the addition of nanosilica particles forming a hybrid composite.

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